

Reasons For The Low Performance Level Of Athletes In The Jordanian Universities From The Point Of View Of Coaches

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Abstract

The study aimed to identify the reasons for the low level of performance of athletes in Jordanian universities from the trainers' (coaches') point of view, as well as the differences in the reasons for the low level of athletes' performance from the trainers' point of view according to the variables of experience and educational qualification. The researchers used the descriptive approach through designing a questionnaire consisting of (30) paragraphs covering (5) aspects, namely: (administrative, technical, health, psychological, and economical capabilities). The sample of study consisted of (9) athletics trainers in Jordanian universities, they were chosen intentionally. The most important results of the study indicated that the most important reasons for the low level of athletes' performance in Jordanian universities from the coaches' point of view are those related to the psychological aspect, and the least effective are those related to the administrative aspect.

Introduction

Universities view student activities as of the main supporters for the educational process (Al-Subaie, 2004). Of the university's goals is to refine the student's personality, develop his skills and abilities, and to prepare him to be responsible and to be able to solve the problems that he may face and invest his spare time in what is useful and beneficial. The achievement of this goal depends on how the university prepares its students mentally, psychologically and socially without the dependence on the curricula and the traditional relationships between the teacher and the student (Al-Othman, 2001), (Owaida, 2011). Von (2007) and Gerber (1996) indicate that student activities improve academic performance and academic excellence and that students participating in the activities have high intelligence and enjoy logical thinking.

The idea of activities and their application in the educational process is an old idea, as old as the emergence of education itself. Education in the ancient civilizations of the Greeks and Romans was activities that focused on rhetoric capability, music, debate, physical education, and drawing (Salem, 2002, p. 25), (Shehata, 1997, p. 21), (Al-Subaie, 2004). Al-Duaij (2002) believes that educational institutions nowadays such as universities, schools and institutes are currently seeking to create an appropriate atmosphere to provide sports, cultural, scientific and social activities that students can invest in their spare time.

The Sports Federation of Jordanian Universities is an umbrella for most of the Jordanian universities' sports, and it aims to sponsor, support, develop and raise the level of the university sports movement by all possible means. It represents Jordanian universities in training courses and conferences held, and coordinate opinions in Arab and international sports conferences (the University of Jordan - Laws, Regulations, and Instructions, 2008). Athletics is one of the basic games in Jordanian universities, which is moving at an uneven and unstable pace and does not live up to the level of ambition despite having a large segment of Jordanian society. Since we are currently living in an era of rapid progress and development in many areas of life, including sports, proper planning is required in order to be able to keep pace with this progress.

Athletics is a competitive physical activity that includes several separate competitions, based on the natural movements of humans such as running, jumping and throwing. Historically, athletics took a form of organized sport during classical times in the ancient Olympics, and athletics was included in the program of the first modern Olympics in Athens in (1896) before the International Association of Athletics Federation was founded in 1912, and since then the program of athletics competitions has developed and become a sport that includes many competitions that differ from each other in the way they perform and the physical characteristics that must be met by those who compete in them, and it was the traditions, status, achievements and comprehensiveness of athletics that placed them in the top rank of sports (elite sport) (Rabadi, 1999), (Ballesteros, 1992).

Researchers interested in university athletics championships have noticed that the results reflect low level of performance of the players. For more than (15) years, no new Jordanian record has been recorded for the men

and women categories in any university athletics' competitions. Based on the foregoing, the researchers believe that administrators responsible for university sports, including athletics, must develop a clear administrative structure and strategy within well-thought-out plans in order to be able to identify the reasons for the low level of male and female athletes in Jordanian universities, and thus provide opportunities to prepare a national team of both sexes capable of achieving the local, Arab and global levels.

Problem of the Study:

The tracker of global athletics and the numbers it has reached, which have been described as exceeding the capabilities of humankind, knows the extent of progress in this sport, and has contributed to its progress in planning, management and modern training based on the latest findings of science in addition to the use of modern scientific and technological methods.

Although one of the most important goals of the Jordanian Universities Sports Federation is to sponsor, support, develop and raise the level of the university sports movement by all possible means, the reality for many university sports activities, including athletics, indicates a continuous decline year after year.

The researchers noticed, through the results of university athletics championships, the low level of performance of Jordanian university team players compared to the players of most Arab and international universities, so that the researchers of this research decided to study the reasons for the decline in the performance of Jordanian universities' athletes from the points of view of coaches. The researchers of this paper think that the results of this study may constitute a reference for those interested in university athletics to find out the reasons for the low technical level in order to address and promote them and raise the level of performance of the game.

Importance of Study:

The importance of the study lies in identifying the reasons for the low level of performance of athletes in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches, which may contribute to the fact that officials in charge of athletics in Jordanian universities have an opportunity to find solutions and proposals to raise the level of athletics in Jordanian universities, so that they become as competitive as other distinguished sports in Jordanian universities.

Objectives of the study:

The study aims to identify:

- Reasons for the low level of athletes' performance in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches.
- The differences in the reasons for the low performance level of athletes in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches, according to the variable (years of experience).
- The differences in the reasons for the low performance level of athletes in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches, according to the variable (educational qualification).

Study questions:

- What are the reasons for the low performance level of athletes in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches?
- Are there any statistically significant differences in the reasons for the low performance level of athletes in Jordanian universities from the coaches' point of view, according to the variable years of experience?
- Are there any statistically significant differences in the reasons for the low performance level of athletes in Jordanian universities from the coaches' point of view, according to the variable of educational qualification?

Terminology:

Performance level: The player's ability to achieve positive results in addition to the correctness and accuracy of high skill performance under the conditions of tournament competitions (procedural definition)

Athletes in Jordanian universities: The players - male and female students - participating in the athletics championships organized by the Sports Federation of Jordanian Universities (procedural definition).

Trainer(Coach): A person who participates in the education and training of sports teams in Jordanian universities (procedural definition).

Athletics: A competitive physical activity that includes several separate competitions, based on the natural movements of humans such as running, jumping and throwing (Rabadi, 1999), (Ballesteros, 1992).

Study Limitations:

-The human determinant: Athletics coaches in Jordanian universities affiliated with the Sports Federation of Jordanian Universities.

-Location Limit: Jordanian universities affiliated with the Sports Federation of Jordanian Universities participating in the Jordanian universities athletics championships.

Time Limit: first semester 2019/2020

Previous Studies:

Fetini (2012) conducted a study that aimed to identify the reasons for the low technical level of the Yemeni gymnastics team players from the point of view of coaches and players, as well as to realize the differences in these reasons between coaches and players. It also aimed to realize the differences between coaches due to the variable of experience in training and qualification, and the difference among athletes due to the variable of period of training. The sample consisted of (26) coaches and (34) players, who were chosen intentionally. The researcher used a questionnaire consisting of (39) items distributed on (5) areas (administrative, technical, psychological, health, materialistic and capabilities). For the purpose of analyzing the answers of the study sample members, the researcher found means, standard deviations, percentages, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results showed that the reasons for the low technical level of the Yemeni gymnastics team players from the coaches' point of view were arranged as follows: technical, administrative, psychological, materialistic, and health reasons, arranged descending respectively. The results also showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the reasons for the low technical level of the Yemeni gymnastics team players from the coaches and players' point of view, while the study found that there are differences according to the educational qualification variable in each of the technical and health reasons between the high school category from the players' point of view according to the variable period of training in the administrative and technical fields is for five years and less, while no differences appeared in the rest of the fields.

Hamdan (2010) conducted a study with the aim of realizing the most important reasons for the low level of tactical performance in the University Basketball Championship in Gaza Strip, in order to improve the level of tactical performance in the game of basketball for university teams. The researcher used the descriptive approach. Population of the study consisted of (75) basketball players representing University teams in Gaza Strip, and they were chosen intentionally. The researcher used a questionnaire consisted of (76) items covering the (physical, skill, tactical, game progression, mental and psychological fields). The researcher found that the reasons for the low tactical performance of players were that burdening them with lots of tasks that surpass their physical abilities. The researcher recommended the continuous training for the team throughout the year in order to prepare for matches and upgrade in all dimensions.

Al-Atrash(2008) also conducted a study entitled "The Effect of a Proposed Training Program for Psychological Skills on Developing the Level of Skill and Tactical Performance among Football Players", which aimed to identify the impact of a proposed training program for some psychological skills to improve skill and tactical performance in football. The researcher used the experimental approach. The research sample consisted of (30) players for the junior category, and of six for the age group (15), and they were chosen intentionally. The program was applied for a period of (8) weeks with (4) training sessions per week. The results of the study indicated that psychological skills programs are effective in improving the level of skill and tactical performance in football, and the researcher recommended the use of psychological skills training programs during training on basic skills and offensive and defensive playing plans in football because of its effective role in developing performance.

Saber (2004) conducted a study aimed to identify some of the factors causing the failure of the tactical aspect in the junior basketball matches. The researcher used the descriptive approach. The sample of the study consisted of (115) junior basketball players from the Premier League clubs and some First-Class clubs in the Arab Republic of Egypt. The tool of study consisted of the personal interview and a questionnaire covering the following dimensions: (training, physical, skill, psychological, mental and match conditions). The most important results of the study concerning the lack of success of the tactical aspect were the poor physical fitness of the players and the lack of adequate tactical preparation for the matches.

Al-Eisari and Al-Jabri(2004) conducted a study that aimed to reveal the reality of educational activities and their impact on academic achievement from the point of view of students and teachers. The researchers used the descriptive approach, and they used questionnaire as a tool to measure the reality of activities and obstacles. The sample consisted of (220) students and (130) teachers. The most important results of their study were that there were high rates of characteristics that distinguish the current reality, with high rates, such as the various school activities, and that the school administration and teachers motivate students and encourage them to practice activities. The study found that there were characteristics that characterize the current reality with low rates, namely, the activities they practice were sufficient, and that school activities were related to the academic subjects, and that students were introduced to the benefits of practicing activities in increasing academic achievement.

Al-Duaij(2002), studied the reasons for the reluctance of Kuwait University' students to practice the activities available for the students at the university, the descriptive approach was used and the questionnaire was used as a tool to measure the most important obstacles in the implementation of student activities at the university, which limit students' benefit from them. The study was applied to a sample of (200) students from different faculties who participated in the activities during that scholastic year. The results showed that 70% of the students did not participate in any activities. Of obstacles to hold student activities were that the students

didn't know the schedules and places to practice those activities, as well as the student's feeling of shyness and reasons that related to the technical aspects and the lack of capabilities and tools to practice the activities.

Procedures of the Study:

Study Approach:

The researchers used the descriptive approach as it suits the nature of the study.

Community of the Study:

Athletics coaches who participate in the Jordanian Universities Athletics Championships.

Sample of the Study:

The study sample consisted of nine coaches from universities participating in the Jordanian universities athletics' championships.

Variables of the Study:

- The independent variable: the trainers' academic qualifications, the trainers' years of experience, as shown in table (1 and 2)

- The dependent variable: the performance level of athletes.

Table (1) Description of the study sample due to years of experience

Variable	Group	Occurrence	Percentage
Years of Experience	5 years or less	2	22.2 %
	More than 5 years	7	77.8 %
Total		9	100 %

Table (2) Description of the study sample due to qualification

Variable	Group	Occurrence	Percentage
Years of Experience	BA Degree	3	33.3 %
	Masters Degree	4	44.4 %
	PhD	2	22.2 %
Total		9	100 %

Tool of the Study:

After returning to the theoretical literature and previous studies: Fatini (2012), Hamdan (2010), Al-Atrash (2008), Saber (2004), Al-Eisari And Al-Jabri (2004), Al-Duaij (2002), Ratib (2001), Allawi (1992), the researchers prepared the tool of the study (the questionnaire) in its initial form, which consisted of (30) paragraphs, and then presented it to (10) PhD degree arbitrators in Physical Education in order to make sure of the appropriateness of the paragraphs for each aspect of study and correctness of the items, adding or deleting items as found appropriate. The study tool consisted finally of (30) paragraphs representing (5) aspects: (administrative, technical, healthy, psychological, and material capabilities).

Scientific treatments for the tool of the study:

Reliability of the tool:

The reliability of the tool was confirmed by using the (Cronbach's alpha) equation for internal consistency, where the value indicated the presence of internal consistency between the paragraphs of the questionnaire and its fields, and this indicates the objectivity and reliability of the tool.

Validity of the tool:

The validity of the content of the tool was determined by presenting it to (10) PhD arbitrators specialized in Physical Education and taking their opinions, and making sure that the tool is reliable in measuring what it was designed for.

Statistical Treatments:

- Mean, standard deviation, and the relative importance of each aspect and for all aspects.
- T-test to compare mean differences.
- Cronbach alpha for internal consistency.
- One way ANOVA test.

Presentation and Discussion of the Results:

To answer the first question of the study: "What are the reasons for the low level of athletes' performance in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches?" the researchers found the means, standard deviations, and the percentage for each paragraph of the field as shown in tables 3, 4, 5, 6, 7.

Table (3) Means, standard deviations and percentage for the items of the Administrative field

No	Item	Mean	SD	Percentage
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1	The internal tournaments organized by the Universities' Sports Federation are insufficient	5.55	0.52	91
2	Universities' Sports Federation hold camps that help improve athletes.	1.22	0.44	24.4
3	The administration of the Universities' Sports Federation is committed to providing a time plan that includes developing athletes.	1.77	0.66	35.4
4	The administration of the Universities' Sports Federation encourages the involvement of athletes in Arab and International competitions.	2.00	2.86	40
5	The Universities' Sports Federation has got administrative staff that are capable to work.	3.22	0.66	64.4
Total degree for the field		2.55	0.27	51

Table (3) shows the Means, Standard Deviations and the percentage for each paragraph of the administrative field. By examining the results of this table, we find that the first paragraph, which states that **"The internal tournaments organized by the universities sports federation are insufficient"** ranked first (M=5.55, SD= 0.52 and a percentage of 91%), this result is in agreement with the studies of Al-Eisari And Al-Jabri (2004) and al-Duaij (2002) that the activities practiced by students are insufficient and lack continuity.

The researchers believe that this result is logical because the lack of holding athletics championships by The Universities Sports Federation and the failure to subject players to sufficient championships leads to their low level, and that the issue of organizing tournaments is closely related to the administrative decisions of The Universities Sports Federation, where the sports federation works to establish one championship during the year and sometimes the tournament is not held due to the lack of financial resources available to The Universities Sports Federation. According to the researchers' knowledge, The Universities Sports Federation (USF) suffers from a lack of financial resources, and researchers believe that this financial problem is due to the decision of the administrative board of the (USF) to hold the Winter Sports Session for universities in the city of Aqaba every year. This drains more than half of the budget of the sports federation on two to three games, and this is contrary to one of the goals of (USF), which is to sponsor the sports movement and the participation of the largest number of university students in tournaments. In addition, the high wages of referees made the Jordanian Universities Sports Federation decide to hold the championship within one day, and limited to little number of events.

The second paragraph, which states that **"Universities' Sports Federation hold camps that help improve athletes"**, ranked last among the paragraphs of the field with (M= 1.22, SD=0.44 and a percentage of 24.4%). This is also logical because coaches believe that this is not important as there are no camps for their athletes, in addition to that, there is a lack of a clear schedule for the dates of the tournaments ahead of time. It is the formation of university team to develop sports, which led to the coaches' indifference to continue training, as one of the responsibilities of the federation is to form university teams. This led to the low level of performance of the players and players. Zeidan (1996) pointed out that to carry out a successful career mission, it is necessary to rely on a good plan in advance.

Table (4) Means, standard deviations and percentage for the items of the Technical field

No	Item	Mean	SD	Percentage
1	Low level of knowledge that coaches of sports activities in universities have.	3.11	0.78	62.2
2	Training hours during one session of training are insufficient to develop the skill level needed for athletes.	3.77	1.09	75.2
3	There is no regular assessment for the coaches by the Department of Sports Activity.	3.77	0.97	75.2
4	Burdening players with extra training responsibilities affects on their competitive level.	3.44	1.01	68.8
5	Number of training sessions is sufficient to improve players' level.	2.55	1.13	51
6	Specialization is a main factor when assigning coaches.	2.88	0.87	57.6
Total degree for the field		3.25	0.34	65

The above table presents the means, standard deviations, and the percentage for each of the paragraphs of the technical field. The results of the table also indicate that the second and third paragraphs, respectively, which state that **"Training hours during one session of training are insufficient to develop the skill level"**

needed for athletes” and the paragraph “**There is no regular assessment for the coaches by the Department of Sports Activity**” have ranked first with (M=3.77, SD=1.09 and 0.97 respectively and a percentage of 75.2%). The researchers believe that the high percentage agreed upon by the sample confirms that there is not enough time to train all athletes in order to raise the level of their performance, because more than half of the universities do not have places to train athletics events, which imposes on universities a financial cost through booking training places and means of transporting for the players, in addition to nutrition and water. Universities have to book fewer hours for training very short before the tournament, and this is not in the interest of improving the performance of athletics players. With regard to the phrase "There is no regular assessment for the coaches by the Department of Sports Activity", the researchers feel, through their knowledge of most university coaches, that there is no control or evaluation by the sports activity departments on the quality of the trainers' work during the exercise. When researchers referred to the records of coaches in the Jordanian Athletics Federation, it was found that more than half of university athletics' coaches do not hold specialized certificates, meaning that they are not specialized in training athletics and are not familiar with the educational steps and technical stages of teaching and training athletics activities. In this context, Al-Jabali (2000) indicates that to implement the training preparation program, a large amount of practical and theoretical information must be available and the ability to apply the preparation depending on the characteristics of the competition.

The fifth paragraph, which states that “**Number of training sessions is sufficient to improve players' level.**” ranked last among the paragraphs of the field (M= 2.55, SD=1.13 and a percentage of 51%). The researchers believe that this result is based on the number of training hours during the exercise is insufficient and is not specialized in the type of exercises used to raise the level of performance of the players. Therefore, the weekly sum of the number of weekly training sessions is not sufficient to raise the level of performance of the players, and consequently there will be a decline in the performance level of athletes. From the researchers' point of view, the trainers place the blame on the insufficient training sessions, whether weekly or daily, to cover their weakness in the field of athletics training, as indicated previously.

Table (5) Means, standard deviations and percentage for the items of the Health field

No	Item	Mean	SD	Percentage
1	Constant and regular medical examinations for athletics players are held on a continuous and regular basis	1.33	0.50	26.6
2	The administration of the Department of Sports Activity is committed to following up the medical cases of athletes.	1.66	0.70	33.2
3	Inadequate rest and sleep during the competition period affect performance	4.66	0.70	93.2
4	Nutrition does not suit the efforts done before, during and after tournaments.	4.33	0.70	66.6
5	Chronic sports injuries hinder players from performing well	4.44	0.72	88.8
6	Athletes are committed to an appropriate recovery program after the effort spent in training and competitions.	2.77	0.83	55.4
Total degree for the field		3.2	0.37	64

Table (5) shows the values of the means, standard deviations, and the percentage of each of the paragraphs of the health field. Looking at the results of this table, we find that the third paragraph, which states “**Inadequate rest and sleep during the competition period affect performance**” ranked first (M= 4.66, SD= 0.70 and a percentage of 93.2%). The researchers believe that the reason of this is due to the lack of awareness of the players about the importance of adequate rest to achieve better results during the competition. Not paying attention to this aspect will lead to a low technical level for the players, and may lead to injuries to the players. The researchers believe that it is necessary to take care of sufficient period of rest and sleep because it is one of the necessary recovery methods to raise the level of fitness and performance of players.

While the first paragraph, “**Constant and regular medical examinations for players are held on a continuous and regular basis**” ranked last among the paragraphs of the field (M= 1.33, SD= 0.50 and a percentage of 26.6%). The researchers believe that the opinion of the study sample in placing this paragraph in the last rank came as a result of their knowledge that their universities do not perform periodic medical examinations for sports players, especially athletes, and the Jordanian Universities Sports Federation does not work on this either and has not directed universities to conduct such examinations.

Table (6) Means, standard deviations and percentage for the items of the psychological domain

No	Item	Mean	SD	Percentage
1	Coaches focus on the long-term and short-term psychological preparation of athletics players	2.88	1.26	57.6
2	Fear of self-failure and appearing at a low level as a result of previous situations negatively affect the level of players	3.66	0.70	73.2

3	The fear of not winning a medal and the intense pressure from the director and the university negatively affects the level of the players	3.33	0.86	66.6
4	The level and importance of the tournament affects the player's condition negatively	3.00	1.22	60
5	The absence of moral support for the player from the federation and the university affects the player negatively	3.88	1.69	77.6
6	The player feels a state of anxiety and fear when he participates for the first time in a tournament	4.44	1.01	88.8
7	The psychological stress of studying affects the level of performance	4.33	0.70	86.6
Total degree for the field		3.65	0.74	73

Table (6) shows the values of means, standard deviations, and the percentage for each of the psychological domain. Examining the results of the table, we find that the sixth paragraph, which states that “**the player feels a state of anxiety and fear when participating for the first time in a tournament**”, has ranked first ($M=4.44$, $SD=1.01$ and a percentage of 88.8%). Ratib (2001) indicates that excessive anxiety and fear of failure and inability to focus on performance can be explained by lack of attention to psychological preparation, which would in return affects players' emotional stability negatively in competitions. The researchers believe that this is due to the lack of experience of the players as a result of their participation for the first time, which leads to their fear and the failure to achieve a positive result, and the lack of experience of the players is a result of the coaches' lack of awareness of the importance of psychological preparation for the players and the delivery of the players to emotional stability and placing them in conditions similar to the competition before participating in the real competition and its impact on the development of the level of performance of the players. Matveive (1981) indicates that one of the most important roles played by the psychologist in the training process is to provide psychological support to the players to face the problems that they may face during training and competitions, and to organize periodic sessions in mental training for players and coaches, and help the players to control emotions, and get rid of manifestations anxiety, tension and agitation.

The first paragraph, which states, “**Coaches focus on the long-term and short-term psychological preparation of athletics players**” ranked last among the paragraphs of the field ($M= 2.88$, $SD=1.26$ and a percentage of 57.6%). The researchers believe that this is due to the shortage of coaches in their knowledge about psychological preparation and its importance in developing the performance of players. The study sample placed this paragraph last because coaches hold the player responsible for his inexperience and his participation for the first time in order to make up for the shortfall they have. Allawi (1992) and Sham'oun (1996) point out the importance of the role of psychological preparation for athletes, as it is an integral part of the process of education, education and training of athletes and preparing them to compete in sports competitions. Researchers believe that universities do not care about the role and importance of the psychologist in the training process.

Table (7) Means, standard deviations and percentage for the items of the Materialistic and Potential domain

No	Item	Mean	SD	Percentage
1	The sports activity of Jordanian universities provides alternative places for training players whose universities do not have playgrounds and shooting fields	1.55	0.72	31
2	The Sports Activity Department provides appropriate support for the preparation of university players	2.33	0.70	46.6
3	The lack of financial support for coaches leads to a low level of players	3.77	0.97	75.4
4	Sports activity in Jordanian universities provides transportation allowance for the players to attend and regular training	2.22	1.39	44.4
5	The physical conditions of the players prevent them from attending the training	3.66	1.22	73.2
6	The sports activity of Jordanian universities provides financial rewards for players who achieve a high and advanced level in tournaments	3.11	1.05	62.2
Total degree for the field		2.77	0.33	55.4

Table (7) shows the means, standard deviations, and the percentage for each of the items of the materialistic domain and potentials, and by looking at the results of this table, we find that the third paragraph,

which states “**The lack of material support for coaches works on the low level of players**” ranked first ($M=3.77$, $SD=0.97$ and a percentage of 75.4%). The researchers believe that the lack of material support for coaches negatively affects the performance of coaches and thus the level of performance of the players. There are no financial incentives for the coach from his university if he gets an achievement, and there are no incentives from the Universities Sports Federation because there is no financial savings caused by wasting half of the budget during the Winter Session in Aqaba, and therefore the coach feels unfair as a result of this painful reality and does not attach importance to training players..

The first paragraph “**Sports activity in Jordanian universities provides alternative places for training players whose universities do not have playgrounds and a throwing field**” ranked last ($M=1.55$, $SD=0.72$ and a percentage of 31%). The researchers realize from the trainers’ point of view that the reason in that this paragraph ranked last because most Jordanian universities do not have athletics stadiums in which to train, even with alternative tools. This is consistent with the recommendation of Al-Huwaish (2018) that it is necessary to work on providing places dedicated to the practice of university activities. The researchers believe that the coaches are indifferent to the existence of training places because they are unable to train athletics and raise the level of the game and because they do not specialize in this game when appointed.

Table (8) Means, standard deviations, and the relative importance for the reasons for the low level of performance of athletics players in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches.

Domain	Mean	SD	Relative Importance
Administrative	2.55	0.27	51
Technical	3.25	0.34	65
Health	3.20	0.37	64
Psychological	3.65	0.74	73
Physical (material)and potential	2.77	0.33	55

Table (8) shows the means, standard deviations, and the relative importance of each field for the reasons for the low level of performance of athletics players in Jordanian universities from the coaches' point of view. The table shows that the first rank among the domains belongs to the psychological domain with a relative importance of 73% and ($M= 3.65$), while the administrative domain ranked last in the ranking of fields with a relative importance of 51% and ($M= 2.55$).

The researchers believe that these results produced by the study are behind the reasons for the low level of performance of athletics players in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches, which do not receive sufficient attention by those responsible for athletics in universities. Therefore, university athletics suffers from obstacles, the most important of which is the psychological one, followed by the technical, and health, then comes the material and capabilities, and finally administrative obstacles.

- To answer the second question, which states: "**Are there statistically significant differences in the reasons for the low level of performance of athletics players in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches according to the variable years of experience?**" the researchers used the t-test to examine the differences between the average estimates of the study sample members about the low level of performance in terms of the experience variable, as shown in table (9).

Table (9) The results of the "t-test to examine the differences between the average estimates of the sample due to experience

Domain	Experience	Mean	SD	T	Sig.	Result
Administrative	5 years or less	2.90	0.14	2.59	0.036	There are significant differences
	More than 5 years	2.45	0.22			
Technical	5 years or less	3.33	0.23	0.32	0.75	No differences
	More than 5 years	3.23	0.38			
Health	5 years or less	3.50	0.23	1.34	0.22	No differences
	More than 5 years	3.11	0.36			
Psychological	5 years or less	3.71	0.20	0.12	0.90	No differences
	More than 5 years	3.63	0.85			
Materialistic and Potential	5 years or less	2.23	0.23	0.251	0.80	No differences
	More than 5 years	2.76	0.37			

	years					
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Calculated T value is at ($\alpha < 0.05$)

Table (9) shows the results of the (t) test according to the variable of experience, as the table shows the calculated (t) value and its level of significance. With the tabular value, we find that the calculated (t) value is greater than the tabular value, which indicates that there are significant differences in the experience variable in this field, while the rest of the calculated (t) values were not significant in the rest of the fields, and the researchers attribute this to the fact that the most experienced trainer has the ability to identify the most important reasons for the low level of performance of players.

- To answer the third question, which states: "**Are there statistically significant differences in the reasons for the low performance level of athletics players in Jordanian universities from the trainers' point of view according to the variable of educational qualification?**" the researchers used the one way ANOVA test to compare the variables about the low level of performance in terms of the educational qualification variable as shown in table no. (10)

Table no. (10) The results of the F-test to examine estimates of the sample about the low level of performance in terms of the variable of educational qualification

Domain	Qualification	Mean	SD	T	Sig.	Result
Administrative	Diploma	2.33	0.23	2.89	0.13	No sig. differences
	Bachelor's	2.75	0.25			
	Master's	0.00	0.00			
	PhD	2.50	0.14			
Technical	Diploma	3.05	0.19	4.65	0.06	No sig. differences
	Bachelor's	3.54	0.28			
	Master's	0.00	0.00			
	PhD	3.00	0.23			
Health	Diploma	3.00	0.44	2.21	0.19	No sig. differences
	Bachelor's	3.45	0.25			
	Master's	0.00	0.00			
	PhD	3.00	0.23			
Psychological	Diploma	4.00	0.42	1.46	0.30	No sig. differences
	Bachelor's	3.75	0.31			
	Master's	0.00	0.00			
	PhD	2.92	1.51			
Materialistic and Potential	Diploma	2.94	0.38	2.00	0.21	No sig. differences
	Bachelor's	2.83	0.19			
	Master's	0.00	0.00			
	PhD	2.41	0.35			

Table (10) refers to the results of the one-way analysis of variance for the reasons for the low level of performance of athletics players in Jordanian universities from the point of view of coaches according to the variable of educational qualification, and by looking at the (p) values mentioned in the table and when comparing them with the tabular value, we find that all (p) values were less than the tabular value, which indicates that there are no statistically significant differences for the fields of study that are attributed to the variable of educational qualification.

Conclusions:

The psychological field was the most important reason for the low performance level of athletics players in Jordanian universities from the coaches' point of view, while the reasons related to the administrative field ranked last in the ranking of fields.

- There is a preference for a coach with great experience in determining the reasons for the low level of performance of athletics players in Jordanian universities from an administrative point of view.

- There were no differences according to the variable of the scientific level of the coaches in determining the reasons for the low level of athletics players in Jordanian universities.

Recommendations:

- The need to pay attention to psychological preparation for its importance, which reflects positively on the performance of the player and coach, and thus on the level of the game.
- Providing a larger number of internal tournaments to gain experience.
- The necessity of providing sufficient time for training as well as providing training camps and participating in external tournaments to ensure opportunities for competing and gaining technical expertise.

- To hold the university session in Amman with a greater number of activities, and thus the budget spent is much less than what is spent on the Winter Session in Aqaba.

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